

Climate Change Rating of Countries 2021 v1.1.3

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Abstract

This work applies a system of Climate Change Rating of countries (CCR). The parameters included in the rating are CO₂ emissions per capita and per GDP, cumulative CO₂ emissions in the last 30 years, and change of emissions in the last 10 years.

The parameters are compared to the world averages conservatively determined for every year.

The CCR for 2021 includes 208 countries, 99.99% of the global CO₂ emissions and population, and 99.82% of the global GDP.

The A-G labels for rating groups are according to the CCR limits. The best rating (A) is for the lowest CCR. The average 2021 rating of Group A is 38 (62% below the world average) and of Group G – 212 (112% above the world average).

The world average CCR value for 2021 is 101.4, equivalent to Group F.

The publication and the linked website include the rating and the details of each country.

Glossary

Σ GDP	cumulative GDP in last 30 years, \$GDP
Ave	average
CCO ₂	global cumulative CO ₂ emissions according to publication [1] [2], CO ₂ emissions produced from fossil fuels and cement production only – land use change is not included, tCO ₂
CCp\$\$\$	country's cumulative CO ₂ emissions in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period
CCp\$\$\$W	weight of parameter CCp\$\$\$
CCR	Climate Change Rating of countries according to this work
CGP	Conservative Global Parameter, decreasing only world parameter applied to the CCR
CO ₂	emissions of Carbon Dioxide, CO ₂
Cp\$	country's CO ₂ emissions per GDP in the last year, tCO ₂ /\$GDP (ton CO ₂ per year, per \$GDP 2017 per year)
Cp\$10	country's change in Cp\$ in last 10 years, tCO ₂ /\$GDP
Cp\$10W	weight of parameter Cp\$10
Cp\$W	weight of parameter Cp\$
CpC	country's CO ₂ emissions per capita in the last year, tCO ₂ /y,cap
CpC10	country's change in CpC in last 10 years, tCO ₂ /y,cap
CpC10W	weight of parameter CpC10
CpCW	weight of parameter CpC
GDP	Gross Domestic Product, constant international \$ 2017, \$GDP/y
Global Warming	global surface temperature change over land+ocean above 1850-1900 baseline, °C
ktCO ₂ /y	kilo-ton CO ₂ = 1,000 metric tons of CO ₂ per year
MtCO ₂ /y	Mega-ton CO ₂ = 1,000,000 metric tons of CO ₂

OWID	Our World in Data – Internet site [1] [2]
Ref	reference
tCO ₂	metric ton of CO ₂
tCO ₂ /y,cap	metric ton of CO ₂ per year, per capita
WB	World Bank
WCCp\$\$	CGP world cumulative CO ₂ emissions in last 30 years per cumulative GDP, tCO ₂ /\$GDP
WCp\$	CGP world CO ₂ emissions per GDP in the last year, tCO ₂ /\$GDP
WCp\$10	CGP world change in Cp\$ in last 10 years, tCO ₂ /\$GDP
WCpC	CGP world CO ₂ emissions per capita in the last year, tCO ₂ /y,cap
WCpC10	CGP world change in CpC in last 10 years, tCO ₂ /y,cap

Climate Change Rating of Countries

Nowagreen Climate Change Rating of Countries is described in the publication [1]. Publication [1] is related to the year 2020. The current publication is related to the Climate Change Rating of Countries in 2021.

Conservative Global Parameters

The CCR world parameters will change every year. There will be years when some world parameters will increase and some will decrease.

To ensure a conservative approach to the CCR, the “*Conservative Global Parameters*” (CGP) will be applied every year and not the actual world averages of this year.

If the value of the world parameter decreases below the value of the previous year Conservative Global Parameter (CGP), the new Conservative Global Parameter (CGP) will change to the actual value of the world parameter. If the value of the world parameter is above the last CGP, the CGP for the current year will remain the same as in the previous year.

Parameters Included in the Rating

Table 1 - Parameters included in the rating

Parameter	Country Symbol	World Symbol	Unit
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	WCpC	tCO2/y,cap
CO2 emissions per GDP	Cp\$	WCp\$	tCO2/\$GDP
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	CCp\$\$	WCCp\$\$	tCO2/\$GDP
Change in CpC in the last 10 years	CPC10	WCPC10	tCO2/y,cap
Change in Cp\$ in the last 10 years	CP\$10	WCP\$10	tCO2/\$GDP

Weights of the CCR Parameters

Table 2 - CCR parameters weight

Parameter	Parameter Symbol	Weight	Weight Symbol
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	CCp\$\$	20%	CCp\$\$W
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	25%	CpCW
CO2 emissions per GDP	Cp\$	25%	Cp\$W
Change in CpC in the last 10 years	CpC10	15%	CpC10W
Change in Cp\$ in the last 10 years	Cp\$10	15%	Cp\$10W
Σ		100%	

A higher value of the calculations' result means worse CCR (more CO2 emissions and lower rating).

Sources of Data

The datasets are from the following sources:

- OWID [2] [3] CO2 emissions produced from fossil fuels and cement production only – land use change is not included
- World Bank (WB) [4] GDP, PPP (constant 2017 international \$)
- United Nations (UN) [5] GDP (constant 2015 \$)

CO2 emissions are without international transport.

More details regarding the datasets may be found in the publications [6] [7].

Table 3 - Dataset [2] [3] [4] [5]

	CO2 emissions	GDP	Population
Source of data	OWID	World Bank/OWID/UN	OWID
Reference	[1] [2] [4]	[3] [4] [1] [7]	[1]
Countries	208	208	208
From year	1990	1990	1990
To year	2021	2021	2021
CO2 from fossil fuels	Yes		
CO2 from cement production	Yes		
CO2 from other sources	No		
Other GHG	No		
Land use change	No		
International transport	No		
Units	MtCO2/y	Constant International \$ 2017	
Resolution	1 ktCO2/y	1 Constant International \$ 2017	

Table 4 - Completeness of data

		Dataset	World	Dataset to World
countries		208	240	86.67%
CO2 emissions	MtCO2/y	36,102	36,102	100.00%
Population	Ex6	7,909	7,909	99.99%
GDP	Ex9\$	134,297	134,535	99.82%

Table 5 - World data for the year 2021

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	World 2021
CO2 emissions in 2021		tCO2/y	36,102,149,000
GDP		\$GDP/y	134,535,410,379,137
Population			7,909,295,104
Cumulative CO2 emissions in the last 30 years		tCCO2	877,679,431,339
Cumulative GDP in the last 30 years		\$\$GDP	2,672,915,852,133,670
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	WCp\$\$	tCCO2/\$\$GDP	0.000328
CO2 emissions per capita	WCpC	tCO2/y,cap	4.56
CO2 emissions per GDP	WCp\$	tCO2/\$GDP	0.000268
CpC before 10 years		tCO2/y,cap	4.72
Cp\$ before 10 years		tCO2/\$GDP	0.000331
Last CpC to CpC before 10 years	CpC10	tCO2/y,cap	97%
Last Cp\$ to Cp\$ before 10 years	Cp\$10	tCO2/\$GDP	81%

Conservative Global Parameters for 2021

Table 6 - Conservative Global Parameters for 2021

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	World 2021	CGP2020	CGP2021
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	WCp\$\$	tCCO2/\$\$GDP	0.000328	0.000333601	0.00032836029
CO2 emissions per capita	WCpC	tCO2/y,cap	4.564522	4.377744993	4.37774499292
CO2 emissions per GDP	WCp\$	tCO2/\$GDP	0.000268	0.000270852	0.00026834682
Last CpC to CpC before 10 years	CpC10	tCO2/y,cap	96.73%	94.7266588%	94.726658766%
Last Cp\$ to Cp\$ before 10 years	Cp\$10	tCO2/\$GDP	81.06%	81.4770622%	81.060836832%

Example for Israel

Table 7 - Basic parameters for CCR for Israel

Parameter	Symbol	Unit	Israel	CGP2021	Israel to CGP2021
CO2 emissions in 2021	CO2	tCO2/y	54,528,500		
GDP	GDP	\$GDP/y	397,152,020,276		
Population			8,900,057		
Cumulative CO2 emissions in the last 30 years	CCO2	tCCO2	1,763,901,000		
Cumulative GDP in the last 30 years	ΣGDP	\$GDP	7,256,842,734,234		
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	CCp\$\$	tCCO2/\$GDP	0.000243	0.000328	74%
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	tCO2/y,cap	6.13	4.38	140%
CO2 emissions per GDP	Cp\$	tCO2/\$GDP	0.000137	0.000268	51%
CpC before 10 years		tCO2/y,cap	9.20		
Cp\$ before 10 years		tCO2/\$GDP	0.000248		
Last CpC to CpC before 10 years	CpC10	tCO2/y,cap	67%	95%	70%
Last Cp\$ to Cp\$ before 10 years	Cp\$10	tCO2/\$GDP	55%	81%	68%

Table 8 - CCR Indexes for Israel in 2021

Parameter	Parameter Symbol	Value	Weight	Index
Cumulative CO2 in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	CCp\$\$	74%	20%	15%
CO2 emissions per capita	CpC	140%	25%	35%
CO2 emissions per GDP	Cp\$	51%	25%	13%
Change in CpC in the last 10 years	CpC10	70%	15%	11%
Change in Cp\$ in the last 10 years	Cp\$10	68%	15%	10%
Σ			100%	83%

Table 9 - Israel's country page on the website [8]

country: Israel (ISR) 2021	
country	Israel
country code	ISR
CCR year	2021
CO2 emissions per capita (CpC), tCO2/y,cap	6.13
CpC to World	140%
CpC weight	35%
CO2 emissions per GDP (Cp\$), tCO2/\$GDP	0.000137
Cp\$ to World	51%
Cp\$ weight	11%
cumulative CO2 emissions in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP (CCp\$\$), tCO2/\$GDP	0.000243
CCp\$\$ to World	74%
CCp\$\$ weight	15%
change in CO2 emissions per capita in the last 10 years (CpC10), tCO2/y,cap	67%
CpC10 to World	70%
CpC10 weight	11%
change in CO2 emissions per GDP in the last 10 years (Cp\$10), tCO2/\$GDP	55%
Cp\$10 to World	70%
Cp\$10 weight	10%
CCR Rating	83
a lower number means less CO2 and a better rating	
country position on the CCR list of a total 208	107
A-G CCR label	D

Countries with CCR Below and Above the World Average

The world CCR in 2021 is 101.4.

Table 10 - Countries with CCR below and above the world average in 2021

	Countries	%	tCO ₂ /y	%
CCR<100	145	70%	9,895,624,017	27%
CCR>100	63	30%	26,196,117,409	73%

70% of the countries have a better CCR rating than the world average in 2021. However, the 30% minority of the countries with CCR worse than the world average is responsible for 73% of the world's CO₂ emissions.

Rating A-G

Rating A-G includes 7 groups.

Table 11 - A-G groups

Rating	min CCR	max CCR	Color
A		50	Light Green
B	51	60	Dark Green
C	61	70	Light Blue
D	71	85	Dark Blue
E	86	100	Violet
F	101	150	Red
G	151		Black

Table 12 - A-G CCR groups in 2021

Rating	countries	Ave CCR	tCO ₂ /y
A	7	38.0	34,633,646
B	31	54.9	469,833,167
C	22	65.5	309,543,829
D	51	77.9	4,132,825,141
E	33	92.7	4,274,034,234
F	35	117.4	4,691,393,418
G	29	211.6	22,179,477,991

Table 13 - A-D E-G CCR groups in 2021

Rating	countries	Ave CCR	tCO2/y	%
A-D	111	67	4,946,835,783	14%
E-G	97	137	31,144,905,643	86%

Table 14 - Group A

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
A	7	38	List #	34,633,646
AGO	Angola	41	4	21,362,730
UGA	Uganda	45	6	5,780,466
COD	Democratic Republic of Congo	28	2	2,606,680
TGO	Togo	45	7	2,342,024
MWI	Malawi	43	5	1,552,192
SOM	Somalia	28	1	610,374
DJI	Djibouti	36	3	379,180

Table 15 - Group B

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
B	31	55		469,833,167
NGA	Nigeria	53	15	136,986,700
BGD	Bangladesh	57	31	93,175,900
SWE	Sweden	54	22	35,849,200
CHE	Switzerland	59	36	34,931,700
LKA	Sri Lanka	56	29	20,780,900
KEN	Kenya	52	14	19,875,430
ETH	Ethiopia	60	37	17,792,540
TZA	Tanzania	51	11	13,058,860
YEM	Yemen	51	8	12,476,640
AFG	Afghanistan	56	30	11,874,210
CIV	Cote d'Ivoire	56	27	11,706,620
CMR	Cameroon	51	9	9,297,280
CRI	Costa Rica	51	10	7,819,510
SLV	El Salvador	60	38	7,204,380
URY	Uruguay	53	18	6,737,870
NIC	Nicaragua	55	24	5,059,780
ALB	Albania	55	26	4,619,110
MLI	Mali	59	33	4,169,760
PSE	Palestine Authority	59	34	3,092,232
HTI	Haiti	53	17	2,875,920
NER	Niger	58	32	2,698,900
TCD	Chad	53	16	1,939,920
MLT	Malta	52	13	1,724,160
MAC	Macao	55	25	1,286,770
SWZ	Eswatini	55	23	1,087,218
GMB	Gambia	56	28	655,699
GNB	Guinea-Bissau	53	19	351,839
SLB	Solomon Islands	59	35	317,925
CAF	Central African Republic	52	12	227,296
LIE	Liechtenstein	54	20	150,950
TUV	Tuvalu	54	21	7,948

Table 16 - Group C

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO ₂ /y
C	22	65		309,543,829
COL	Colombia	64	45	91,703,300
PER	Peru	63	43	56,282,200
HKG	Hong Kong	61	39	31,664,400
DNK	Denmark	68	56	29,576,900
GHA	Ghana	67	53	21,312,800
SDN	Sudan	70	59	21,038,240
PAN	Panama	67	52	13,031,610
HND	Honduras	69	57	10,897,840
PRY	Paraguay	66	51	8,576,570
BEN	Benin	69	58	7,755,820
GIN	Guinea	64	46	4,841,780
MDG	Madagascar	62	42	4,244,352
RWA	Rwanda	70	60	1,754,532
MNE	Montenegro	64	47	1,751,384
SLE	Sierra Leone	61	40	1,299,406
LBR	Liberia	65	49	1,195,258
TLS	East Timor	63	44	736,328
BDI	Burundi	65	48	692,908
CPV	Cape Verde	66	50	667,694
VCT	Saint Vincent and the Grenadines	68	54	213,670
VUT	Vanuatu	68	55	174,859
STP	Sao Tome and Principe	61	41	131,978

Table 17 - Group D

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
D	51	78		4,132,825,141
IDN	Indonesia	76	79	619,277,000
BRA	Brazil	71	62	488,881,000
MEX	Mexico	73	64	407,206,000
GBR	United Kingdom	75	78	346,775,000
ITA	Italy	82	99	328,687,000
FRA	France	73	66	305,963,000
EGY	Egypt	74	70	249,624,000
ESP	Spain	79	89	233,650,000
PAK	Pakistan	74	68	229,512,700
PHL	Philippines	75	76	144,263,900
CHL	Chile	84	109	85,447,000
VEN	Venezuela	78	86	79,746,600
ROU	Romania	77	84	79,327,000
MAR	Morocco	83	105	70,577,600
ISR	Israel	83	107	54,528,500
ECU	Ecuador	80	93	41,321,700
PRT	Portugal	71	61	40,797,200
IRL	Ireland	83	103	37,540,100
SGP	Singapore	73	65	32,506,800
DOM	Dominican Republic	73	67	28,922,110
JOR	Jordan	84	110	25,593,700
BOL	Bolivia	85	111	23,321,670
CUB	Cuba	75	77	22,057,400
GTM	Guatemala	74	72	20,327,100
HRV	Croatia	79	90	17,701,500
LTU	Lithuania	83	102	13,880,900
SEN	Senegal	78	87	13,597,920
PNG	Papua New Guinea	80	94	8,509,570
ZMB	Zambia	76	82	7,676,190
LVA	Latvia	74	73	7,266,240
MOZ	Mozambique	83	104	7,156,210
MKD	North Macedonia	83	106	6,851,550
ARM	Armenia	82	101	6,806,040
BWA	Botswana	84	108	6,499,920
GAB	Gabon	74	69	5,712,480
BFA	Burkina Faso	79	92	5,698,260
MDA	Moldova	78	88	5,601,400
GNQ	Equatorial Guinea	74	71	5,224,790
MUS	Mauritius	82	100	4,471,670
MRT	Mauritania	76	80	4,118,110
NAM	Namibia	77	83	4,014,830
SSD	South Sudan	82	98	1,582,060
FJI	Fiji	79	91	1,470,400
PYF	French Polynesia	76	81	949,800
BLZ	Belize	75	75	689,322
LCA	Saint Lucia	81	97	485,927
GRD	Grenada	80	96	319,210
COM	Comoros	75	74	298,171
VGB	British Virgin Islands	72	63	158,529
DMA	Dominica	78	85	158,529
KIR	Kiribati	80	95	71,533

Table 18 - Group E

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
E	33	93		4,274,034,234
IND	India	95	135	2,709,685,000
TUR	Turkey	91	124	446,205,000
THA	Thailand	91	127	278,495,600
ARG	Argentina	86	113	186,448,400
NLD	Netherlands	98	139	141,046,000
AUT	Austria	94	131	64,625,700
GRC	Greece	86	114	56,309,200
HUN	Hungary	86	112	48,454,700
NOR	Norway	91	125	40,918,600
FIN	Finland	89	118	37,602,300
MMR	Myanmar	93	130	36,306,740
NZL	New Zealand	92	129	33,789,800
TUN	Tunisia	90	121	31,582,780
SRB	Serbia	96	136	30,869,000
SYR	Syria	94	132	27,000,800
NPL	Nepal	91	123	14,173,070
BIH	Bosnia and Herzegovina	96	137	13,566,360
SVN	Slovenia	86	115	12,549,380
ZWE	Zimbabwe	90	122	11,296,150
GEO	Georgia	88	116	11,009,760
KGZ	Kyrgyzstan	88	117	9,308,100
JAM	Jamaica	94	133	7,689,730
CYP	Cyprus	100	142	7,600,400
XKX	Kosovo	98	138	5,644,364
GUY	Guyana	90	120	3,087,820
BHS	Bahamas	100	144	2,386,470
LSO	Lesotho	100	143	2,282,164
BTN	Bhutan	99	141	1,522,088
BRB	Barbados	95	134	1,125,300
ATG	Antigua and Barbuda	99	140	468,696
AND	Andorra	89	119	452,888
WSM	Samoa	91	126	294,080
KNA	Saint Kitts and Nevis	92	128	237,794

Table 19 - Group F

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO2/y
F	35	117	List #	4,691,393,418
JPN	Japan	112	161	1,067,396,000
DEU	Germany	101	145	674,754,000
KOR	South Korea	143	179	616,075,000
POL	Poland	126	171	328,579,000
VNM	Vietnam	118	162	326,013,300
TWN	Taiwan	138	176	282,857,000
MYS	Malaysia	122	167	256,049,200
UKR	Ukraine	123	170	201,859,000
IRQ	Iraq	134	175	185,581,100
DZA	Algeria	119	165	176,269,400
UZB	Uzbekistan	141	177	121,631,600
CZE	Czechia	123	169	97,137,000
BEL	Belgium	105	152	95,722,000
BLR	Belarus	128	172	59,602,400
BGR	Bulgaria	110	157	42,560,100
AZE	Azerbaijan	106	153	38,492,700
SVK	Slovakia	104	151	35,308,000
LBN	Lebanon	121	166	24,958,940
KHM	Cambodia	129	173	19,028,610
EST	Estonia	111	159	10,449,000
TJK	Tajikistan	143	178	10,336,420
LUX	Luxembourg	118	163	8,354,600
ISL	Iceland	108	154	3,374,960
SUR	Suriname	111	160	2,793,200
MDV	Maldives	104	150	2,118,174
ABW	Aruba	103	149	858,130
ERI	Eritrea	109	156	820,600
SYC	Seychelles	102	146	568,279
BMU	Bermuda	110	158	547,960
GRL	Greenland	109	155	510,660
TCA	Turks and Caicos Islands	130	174	341,183
TON	Tonga	102	148	174,859
FSM	Micronesia (country)	118	164	158,962
COK	Cook Islands	123	168	91,403
MSR	Montserrat	102	147	20,678

Table 20 - Group G

Rating	Count	CCR	CCR	tCO ₂ /y
G	29	212		22,179,477,991
CHN	China	158	182	11,472,370,000
USA	United States	155	180	5,007,310,000
RUS	Russia	175	190	1,755,545,000
IRN	Iran	172	189	748,879,000
SAU	Saudi Arabia	205	195	672,380,000
CAN	Canada	162	184	545,635,000
ZAF	South Africa	163	186	435,929,000
AUS	Australia	167	187	391,186,000
KAZ	Kazakhstan	213	197	276,684,000
ARE	United Arab Emirates	203	194	204,086,800
KWT	Kuwait	259	203	106,134,200
QAT	Qatar	299	206	95,667,200
TKM	Turkmenistan	260	204	83,007,000
OMN	Oman	212	196	80,991,100
LBY	Libya	179	191	74,525,000
PRK	North Korea	255	202	56,380,600
MNG	Mongolia	320	207	50,315,900
BHR	Bahrain	271	205	39,016,100
TTO	Trinidad and Tobago	326	208	36,124,000
LAO	Laos	219	198	20,777,510
BRN	Brunei	224	199	10,480,530
COG	Congo	169	188	7,464,370
NCL	New Caledonia	250	200	5,496,270
CUW	Curacao	196	193	1,843,760
SXM	Sint Maarten (Dutch part)	190	192	647,890
PLW	Palau	253	201	238,444
MHL	Marshall Islands	157	181	158,962
AIA	Anguilla	163	185	144,744
NRU	Nauru	160	183	59,611

World CCR Rating

Table 21 - World CCR

Parameter	2021	CGP2021	2021/CGP	Weight	CCR
Cumulative CO ₂ in the last 30 years per cumulative GDP in the same period	0.000328	0.000328	100%	20%	20.0%
CO ₂ emissions per capita	4.56	4.38	104%	25%	26.1%
CO ₂ emissions per GDP	0.000268	0.000268	100%	25%	25.0%
Last CpC to CpC before 10 years	97%	95%	102%	15%	15.3%
Last Cp\$ to Cp\$ before 10 years	81%	81%	100%	15%	15.0%
Σ				100%	101.4%

In 2021 the world CCR was 101.4, which is Group F, Red group.

The main reason for the change is the world's CO₂ emissions per capita, which increased in 2021 by 4.3%.

Climate Change Rating of Countries on the Website

The Climate Change Rating of countries according to this work for the years 2020 and 2021 is available on the website [8].

Table 22 - Climate Change Rating of Countries 2021 on the Website [8]

Nowgreen Climate Change Rating of Countries - CCR 2021 sorted by country code				
for more details click on country code				
country code	country	CCR	position on CCR list	A-G Rating
ABW	Aruba	103	149	F
AFG	Afghanistan	56	30	B
AGO	Angola	41	4	A
AIA	Anguilla	143	185	G
ALB	Albania	55	26	B
AND	Andorra	89	119	E
ARE	United Arab Emirates	203	194	G
ARG	Argentina	86	113	E
ARM	Armenia	82	101	D
ATG	Antigua and Barbuda	99	140	E
AUS	Australia	167	187	G
AUT	Austria	94	131	E
AZE	Azerbaijan	106	153	F
BDI	Burundi	65	48	C
BEL	Belgium	105	152	F
BEN	Benin	69	58	C
country code	country	CCR	position on CCR list	A-G Rating
BFA	Burkina Faso	79	92	D
BGD	Bangladesh	57	31	B
BGR	Bulgaria	110	157	F

Changes in this Version

- o Minor editorial corrections.

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